

ЕКОНОМІЧНІ ПРОБЛЕМИ РОЗВИТКУ ГАЛУЗЕЙ ТА ВИДІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

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Enterprise risk management in force majeure circumstances

The subject of the study is the enterprise risk management system in modern conditions using economic tools.

The purpose of writing the article is to justify the feasibility of using economic tools of anti-crisis management on the example of subjects of the hospitality industry, as well as the advantages of financing the company's risk of possible losses due to the action of various factors and the development of a system of criteria for the effectiveness of the use of economic tools.

The methodology of the work is the provisions of the theories of normative economy and creative industries. On the basis of a systemic approach, the factors influencing the management of economic activity risks in Ukraine have been identified. Using the methods of structuring and synthesis, the strengths and weaknesses of the economic development potential were identified and proposals were developed to strengthen the role of certain economic instruments in ensuring the functioning of the tourism sector and solving the problems of risk management of hotel and restaurant business enterprises.

Results of the work – The role of new tools and methods for risk management in crisis conditions was determined, new threats and risks of economic entities generated in war conditions were outlined, factors restraining the development of economic tools were identified, the factors of their activation were revealed and measures were proposed to deal with them expansion, the expediency of introducing and using new insurance tools and methods for risk management in modern crisis states of the economy is substantiated.

Conclusions – Insurance remains the most effective economic tool of risk management in conditions of financial and economic crises, in particular in force majeure circumstances of conducting business as a result of military operations on the territory of Ukraine. In the field of the hospitality industry, the concept of «economic risk» has been formulated, which is defined as the possibility of accidental occurrence of unwanted losses, measured in value equivalent. In order to give this concept an operational meaning, it is necessary to classify risks according to various criteria based on the structural characteristics of the risk, information support and features of risk definition. For specific risks, specific classification criteria related to the specificity of risks during war can also be used. In this context, the classification of risks according to adequately selected criteria can improve the understanding of the sources of economic risk, methods of its minimization and compensation. However, insurance as a risk management tool is the most effective, despite the fact that its use has

certain limitations. At the state level, an important feature of the risk management system is the involvement of risk reduction methods, since the state's ability to avoid risk during war and to transfer risk to third parties is quite limited. At the macroeconomic level, it is expedient to create state sectoral insurance funds with the involvement of foreign reparation funds. Outsourcing the risk management process is particularly effective. The instrument of risk management in this case will be the state program of risk management and minimization after the war period.

Keywords: economic instruments, risk management, risk control, force majeure.

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Ризик менеджмент підприємства в форс–мажорних обставинах

Предмет дослідження – система управління ризиками підприємства в сучасних умовах з використанням економічних інструментів.

Метою написання статті є обґрунтування доцільності використання економічних інструментів антикризового управління на прикладі суб'єктів індустрії гостинності, а також переваг фінансування підприємством ризику можливих втрат унаслідок дії різноманітних факторів та розробки системи критеріїв ефективності використання економічних інструментів.

Методологія проведення роботи – положення теорій нормативної економіки та креативних індустрій. На основі системного підходу визначено чинники, що впливають на управління ризиками господарської діяльності в Україні. Методами структурування та синтезу виявлено сильні та слабкі сторони потенціалу економічного розвитку та розроблено пропозиції щодо посилення ролі певних економічних інструментів у забезпеченні функціонування туристичної сфери та вирішення проблем управління ризиком підприємств готельно–ресторанного бізнесу.

Результати роботи – Визначено роль нових інструментів та методів для управління ризиками в кризових умовах, окреслено нові загрози та ризики економічних суб'єктів, які генеруються в умовах війни, виявлено фактори, що стримують розвиток економічних інструментів, розкрито чинники їх активізації та запропоновано заходи щодо їх розширення, обґрунтовано доцільність впровадження та використання нових інструментів та методів страхування для управління ризиками в сучасних кризових станах економіки.

Висновки – Найбільш ефективним економічним інструментом ризик–менеджменту в умовах фінансово–економічних криз, зокрема у форс–мажорних обставинах ведення бізнесу внаслідок військових дій на території України залишається страхування. У сфері індустрії гостинності сформульовано поняття «економічний ризик», який визначається як можливість випадкового виникнення небажаних збитків, вимірюваних у вартісному еквіваленті. Для надання цьому поняттю операційного змісту необхідно класифікувати ризики за різними критеріями на основі структурних характеристик ризику, інформаційного забезпечення та особливостей визначення ризиків. Для конкретних ризиків також можна використовувати специфічні критерії класифікації, пов'язані зі специфікою ризиків під час війни. У цьому контексті класифікація ризиків за адекватно обраними критеріями може покращити розуміння джерел виникнення економічного ризику, методів його мінімізації та відшкодування. Проте страхування як інструмент управління ризиком є найбільш ефективним, не зважаючи на те, що його використання має певні обмеження. На рівні держави важливою особливістю системи управління ризиком є залучення методів скорочення ризику, оскільки можливості держави по ухиленню від ризику під час війни і з передачі ризику третім особам досить обмежені. На макроекономічному рівні доцільно створення державних галузевих страхових фондів із залученням репараційних закордонних коштів. Зокрема ефективною є передача процесу управління ризиком в аутсорсинг. Інструментом проведення ризик–менеджменту в цьому випадку буде державна програма управління та мінімізації ризиків післявоєнного періоду.

Ключові слова: економічні інструменти, ризик–менеджмент, управління ризиками, форс–мажорні обставини.

Formulation of the problem. With the help of foreign financial support, Ukraine's economy has been on a war footing for the past six months. Priority attention is given to strategically important branches of the military–industrial complex, preservation of infrastructure and logistics for the movement of military and related goods, as well as labor and civilian resources. In such conditions, the tourism industry has undergone significant existential changes, turning into a service industry for the movement and livelihood of refugees from regions subject to military operations. Even the vacation period did not provide a tourist flow that could stabilize the functioning of hospitality enterprises. Today, in Ukraine, the main deterrents to stabilizing the work of enterprises in this area are operational risks associated with military actions, financial instability in the country, as well as the uncertainty of the legislative framework regarding international investments and the development of business tourism [1, 4, 7–11, 12]. The significant payback period of post-war projects is less attractive compared to other sectors of the economy, as it does not correspond to the risks of investing in this segment [1, 5, 12].

The tourism industry is a specific sector of the economy, which has a huge multiplier effect. This gives impetus to the development of not only the hotel market, retail and the service sector, but also the economy as a whole. Therefore, if it is possible to create positive business expectations in this area after the end of the war in Ukraine, the flow of international investments in this area will increase [2, 3]. Diversification of tourism is one of the driving forces of the development of the hospitality industry. Green, rural, gastronomic, medical, extreme, entertainment, sports and even international military tourism can provide an increase in the flow of tourists. However, today it is advisable to focus on domestic tourism, which will be facilitated by advertising and brand recognition of tourist regions of Ukraine.

Since 2018, the total number of tourist accommodation facilities in Ukraine has decreased by 25%, while an increase in their total number in the Lviv region by 5.4% was observed. The number of hotel and restaurant establishments provided by legal entities and entrepreneurs decreased by 17.2% in Ukraine as a whole, but increased in: Ivano–Frankivsk region – by 20%; in the Kyiv region it decreased by 32.5%; in Kyiv increased by 3.4%; Khmelnytskyi region – by 3.7%; Lvivskyi – by almost 2.5%. In other regions,

significant changes have taken place in the distribution of accommodation: the number of apartments has almost doubled, and the number of hostels for internally displaced persons who have lost their homes in the occupied territories is gradually increasing. The management of many hotels is revising the policy of providing services and is beginning to be more meticulous in determining the category of hotels and their compliance with international standards, in particular, the safety of accommodation and service. The spread of temporary accommodation facilities for immigrants, which began to appear in the western regions, is also positive. However, there is a need to improve the quality and range of services, which is connected with the constantly growing demands of consumers in the field of security and the introduction of modern means of communication. Modern Ukraine is characterized by forest and household fires at industrial, communal and residential facilities, emissions and discharges of harmful substances into the atmospheric air and surface water, physical and radio wave pollution by explosive substances, which cause significant losses to third parties and the economy of the state as a whole. Complications of technological processes of production of energy resources, including from alternative sources, the use of high-speed and multi-ton vehicles lead to the appearance of new risks and environmental losses. Therefore, adequately constructed risk management strategies in the hospitality industry are the key to success on this path.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The scientific works of well-known Ukrainian and foreign scientists are devoted to the analysis of the problems of risk management of economic entities, among them the works of: V.V. Vitlinskyi, V.M. Granaturova, O.L. Ustenko, O.I. Yastremsky, A.D. Stefanycha, A.P. Algina, G.B. Kleiner, I.T. Balabanova, E.A. Utkina, S.M. Ilyashenko, V.V. Cherkasova, G.V. Chernova, V.V. Hlushchenko, M.V. Khokhlov, and others, which were assessed the degree of risk, determining the causes and consequences of its occurrence for the economy. Separate issues related to the use of various tools of protection against negative consequences in the integrated risk management system of the enterprise were investigated in the works of I.A. Blanka, A.V. Shegdy, A.O. Starostina, L.I. Abalkina, A.P. Ivanova and others. [1 – 8], However, the strategy of using these tools in the conditions of martial law and limited public fi–

nances remains insufficiently elucidated. Ensuring the steady development of Ukraine's economy in the post-war period requires the deepening of theoretical and practical improvements in the management of economic activity, the introduction of a comprehensive system of assessment and management of the economic risk of enterprises, in particular in the service sector.

The purpose of the article. The purpose of the article is to substantiate the expediency of using a complex of anti-crisis management tools in the activities of enterprises of the hospitality industry and sustainable development, as well as the advantages of financing the risk of possible losses due to various factors.

Presenting main material. The risk of post-war economic activity acts as a tool for responding to changes in the external environment of the enterprise's functioning. Risk management is defined as a set of management actions [1, 6–9, 11, 12] aimed at their adequate consideration and minimization in management decisions. The analysis of modern approaches to risk management made it possible to determine the algorithm of its successive stages, which consists of diagnosing the problem; risk analysis; determination of the risk position of the enterprise based on the results of risk assessment; development and implementation of the main action program for adjusting the degree of risk; monitoring and control of the risk management process. The creation of a risk management system should ensure the high efficiency of management decision-making to achieve the strategic and tactical goals of any industry enterprise [7, 9, 11]. The use of the risk management algorithm allows you to adjust the development strategy taking into account the degree of risk, increase the effectiveness of their operation.

The main goal of risk management is the prevention of financial losses of the enterprise in the conditions of crisis phenomena, such as pandemics, man-made and natural disasters, terrorist and military actions. Anti-crisis management is designed to prevent and overcome the financial crisis of the enterprise, as well as to minimize such negative consequences as the bankruptcy of the enterprise. Anti-crisis management is based on the constant readiness of management to respond; preventive actions; urgency and adequacy of response; complexity of solutions; adaptability of

management and prioritization of the use of internal resources [1, 3, 5].

The general meaning of risk management is the management of circumstances and economic relations arising in the process of such management. In the conditions of the unpredictability of the economic situation, the danger of crisis phenomena in the enterprise's activities and the threat of its bankruptcy, risk management is a component of the general concept of anti-crisis management of the enterprise. According to statistics, entrepreneurs lose their assets under certain force majeure circumstances approximately once every five years.

Risks can be caused by the dependence of business on changes in the economic policy of the government, changes in the priority areas of its activity, on the vulnerability of the financial system in specific conditions such as martial law.

In general, the following risks can be distinguished:

- non-fulfillment (or improper fulfillment) of contractual obligations;
- interruptions in production and commercial activity due to force majeure circumstances, personnel errors, illegal actions of third parties or global threats (pandemic, war, natural and man-made disasters);
- a decrease in the volume of sales of goods (works, services) as a result of competition, a decrease in the solvent demand of consumers;
- losses of money of entrepreneurs who are in financial and credit institutions;
- partial or complete loss of real/portfolio investments and income from them as a result of:
 - natural events affecting the investment object;
 - mistakes of the business project that is the object of investment;
 - illegal actions of third parties;
 - deterioration of the financial and economic condition, insolvency of the issuer of securities, changes in the refinancing rate of the NBU;
- innovative risks are risks from the implementation of the results of research and design development;
- increase in costs for the production and sale of goods (works, services) as a result of inflationary price growth, changes in currency exchange rates, occurrence of unforeseen costs as a result of natural disasters, court costs, increase in material costs, etc.;
- losses in connection with the loss of property rights to the entrepreneur's property and his non-

property rights to intellectual property objects, trademarks, etc., as a result of a military invasion;

- the debtor entrepreneur loses the ability to fulfill his obligations to the creditor under the credit agreement as a result of the deterioration of the solvency or bankruptcy of the guarantor, guarantor;
- losses of the entrepreneur due to personnel errors;
- bankruptcy of an entrepreneur;
- loss of business reputation of the enterprise or institution, etc.

All possible losses require the development of an appropriate anti-crisis management mechanism in order to avoid them. Of course, the risk for a particular entrepreneur is individual, therefore the use of certain methods is also individual and determined by real economic circumstances.

The following are general means of solving risks:

- avoidance – avoidance of risk-related activities, actions, measures;
- maintenance – assumes that losses will be covered by the economic entity independently;
- transfer to a party – an economic entity transfers its own risk to another entity, such as an insurance company;
- reducing the degree of risk – reducing the probability and size of losses.

Various methods are used to reduce the degree of risk [11, 12]: diversification; obtaining additional information about the selection and results; limitation; self-insurance; insurance; currency risk insurance; hedging; acquisition of control over activities in related industries; accounting and evaluation of the share of the use of specific funds of the company in its general funds, etc. The subject of entrepreneurial activity is obliged to choose such a strategy that will allow him to reduce the degree of risk as much as possible. Most often, companies resort to self-insurance and insurance. Self-insurance is a method of creating an insurance fund in a decentralized form by any business entity in order to ensure uninterrupted risk production. The economic entity forms and uses funds in monetary form and (or) reserves of raw materials, materials, spare parts, etc. due to unfavorable economic conditions, delays by customers in payments for delivered products, etc. The procedure for using the funds of insurance funds for self-insurance is provided by the statute of the economic entity. Also, self-insurance can be considered as a risk taken

by the insured (owner). In order to save insurance costs, large industrial, aviation and other companies create their own insurance funds (reserves) to cover losses caused by adverse events. However, self-insurance contradicts the economic nature of insurance and cannot fully replace it, which is especially evident in the event of large (catastrophic) losses, the size of which can significantly exceed the available funds and affect the financial condition of the business entity.

Force majeure circumstances make changes in the usual life of enterprises, forcing them to take a new look at the financial instruments of the market and, above all, at insurance. Insurance is one of the most commonly used methods of risk management. The essence of insurance is that the risk bearers (insureds) transfer their responsibility for bearing the burden of risk to an insurer specializing in such operations for a specified fee. The limited opportunities of insurance companies to accept large risks for insurance are eliminated by means of special approaches to the redistribution of responsibility for covering the corresponding loss among other participants of the insurance market.

Making a decision on risk insurance is carried out in several stages:

- 1) selection of risks to be insured;
- 2) choosing the type of insurance coverage;
- 3) choosing an insurance company;
- 4) conducting negotiations on the terms of the insurance contract and its conclusion;
- 5) analysis of the effectiveness of insurance and decision-making on concluding a contract.

However, insurance as a method of risk management is not a universal tool and the use of insurance has its limitations, which may be related to the type of risk, the relationship between the parties to the insurance transaction, and their attitude to risk. The lack of clear decision-making criteria regarding the choice of insurance as a method of risk management does not allow automatic classification of risks into those that are subject to insurance and those that cannot be insured.

It is possible to determine the conditions under which it is advisable for the policyholder to conclude an insurance contract, and in which case it is worth refusing to conclude an insurance contract with an insurance company (resort to self-insurance), that is, it is about the cost of risk financing, which is understood as the search and mobiliza-

tion of monetary resources for the implementation of preventive measures and preventing losses in the event of adverse events. At the same time, the amount of insurance compensation cannot exceed the amount of the insured amount, that is, the amount for which the insured object is insured (the value of the insurance policy). This means that the expected result for the enterprise will always be negative. Therefore, from the position of the insured, the question arises about the feasibility of creating personal insurance funds or, at the macro level, state sectoral insurance funds.

When making a decision on risk insurance for an enterprise, one should evaluate not the expected result, but the usefulness of making a decision on insurance. The nature of the utility function $U(z)$, where z is income, largely depends on making a decision: to take or not to take a risk. And a positive decision to take a risk is made when the utility of the overall result turns out to be positive. In other words, a negative result is justified if, by risking less, you can avoid greater losses. The maximum amount of the insurance premium that should be paid to the entrepreneur for insurance protection can be determined as follows:

$$- < + + 1rdPFZr, \quad (1)$$

where r is the average return on capital of the enterprise involved in economic turnover;

d – the percentage of return of the reserve fund created at the enterprise;

P – amount of insurance premium;

F – the amount of the own reserve fund, which is formed in case of refusal of insurance;

Z is the amount of losses from risk factors [10, c. 226].

In the opposite case, it is worth resorting to self-insurance – the creation of an industry insurance fund.

Insurance, as a mechanism of risk management, has inherent shortcomings that cannot be eliminated using a more complete knowledge of the object of insurance and the risks associated with it. These disadvantages include:

- forced financing of the insurer's management costs and profits;
- expenses related to the redistribution of loss between policyholders;
- internal risks of the insurer.

However, in economically developed countries, an insurance policy for a business entity is a necessary condition for doing business.

The transfer of responsibility for compensation of a possible loss to another subject is one of the most frequently used methods of financing risks that can be applied in the field of hotel business and tourism. The essence of this risk management method is to transfer responsibility to an insurance company specializing in such operations. The use of insurance means a reduction in participation, and sometimes even a complete refusal of the company itself (hotel, restaurant, tour operator) to participate in the coverage of losses due to the transfer of its risk to the insurance company for a certain fee. The mechanism of risk transfer through enterprise insurance allows an insurance professional not only to solve specific protection problems, but also has far-reaching consequences and affects the economy of the country as a whole.

Bearers of economic risk are both individual subjects and their groups, which are considered in terms of industrial and economic activity and personal and social life. All economic aspects of insurance are also revealed against the background of their business, economic and personal activities. Ensuring and maintaining the standard of living and well-being of an individual and an individual family, insurance is a tool for ensuring the financial and social protection of the population. In addition to the state social insurance, commercial insurance is one of the forms of social assistance that makes it possible to maintain the achieved level of human well-being. In the conditions of a market economy, insurance becomes almost the only tool that guarantees the financial protection of the interests of citizens against accidental events (fire, accident, traffic accident) that lead to the loss of property, work capacity and health, the emergence of new costs.

Even if an insurance contract is concluded, the insurance premium is paid, and the insured event has not occurred (the payment remains with the insurer), the insurer develops a sense of confidence and security, which is an important factor that stabilizes the psychological stability of a person. From such positions, insurance is not just a compensatory mechanism for incurred losses, but also a means of supporting a person for normal life activities, which is especially important for entrepreneurs in the conditions of martial law.

Insurance as a risk management tool is not universal. Among all cases, it is impossible to define a clear boundary between risks that are not subject

to insurance and risks that are advisable to insure, that is, the criteria for definition are subjective. Therefore, other risk management tools are often used today, even for those risks that have traditionally been mastered by insurance. Limitations of insurance may be related to the type of risk, the relationship of the parties, the attitude to risk.

Limitation by type of risk is a key factor in understanding the essence of insurance. It should be noted that only economic risks can be insured, i.e. those whose damage is expressed in the form of value. However, not all economic risks can be insured, but only according to the classification according to the characteristics of danger and vulnerability. Therefore, the relevant criteria cannot serve as a sign of the expediency of applying insurance.

According to the classification according to other groups of criteria, the situation is different. Thus, according to the classification according to the characteristic of risk propensity, it is important to divide into pure and speculative risks. Insurance is often used to manage the risks of the first group, hedging and other alternative methods are used for the second.

Diversification of risks and the absence of their mutual influence are of fundamental importance for classification according to the characteristics of interaction with other risks. Mass and general risks are preferred for insurance, but unique and private risks can also be insurable. In the latter case, the availability of reliable quantitative information plays a key role. In addition, to solve the issue of insurance, it is necessary to simultaneously take into account the classification by the amount of risk.

Insurance is definitely necessary in the presence of catastrophic risks. In most cases, it is the basis of risk management programs, especially since sometimes its implementation is required by law [11], the so-called mandatory types of insurance. However, an individual insurance company does not always have the opportunity to take a large risk for insurance, but for such situations there are special approaches for redistributing this catastrophic risk among market participants (for example, reinsurance) [5, 7, 10].

The form of insurance transactions and especially its legal basis can impose significant restrictions on the use of insurance as a risk management tool [10]. This is manifested in the following cases:

- prohibition of insurance of certain types of risk (risks related to illegal actions, participation in

games, lotteries and betting, as well as costs related to the release of hostages);

- restrictions on insurance contracts concluded within the framework of the relevant jurisdiction (first of all, which wording can be recognized as insignificant).

Legal restrictions on insurance transactions in Ukraine are contained in the Civil Code of Ukraine and the Law of Ukraine «On Insurance». Certain restrictions can be imposed not only by contract, but also by insurance companies unilaterally. An example can be various ethical and generally accepted rules developed and supported by industry associations (for example, unions and associations of insurers).

Due to the peculiarities of the attitude to risk, the main requirement is the lack of interest of the risk bearer in the occurrence of an adverse event. If the risk carrier can affect the probability of occurrence and/or the size of the loss, this creates conditions for various types of fraud. Therefore, the risk transferred to insurance must be determined by random circumstances that do not depend on the will and actions of the risk bearer. Fulfillment of this requirement is regulated by legislation and partly by tradition. At the same time, the requirements of the absence of dependence between the occurrence of an adverse event and the actions of the risk bearer look quite ideal. Violation of this requirement, encountered in practice, is reduced to one of the following effects:

1. Adverse selection. It is explained by the fact that decisions about insurance are made by interested persons. Persons with an increased risk will be more interested in concluding insurance contracts than persons with a lower risk.

2. Opportunistic behavior (moral hazard). This effect is related to the conscious or unconscious possibility of influence of the risk bearer on the probability of occurrence.

Although it is almost impossible to completely prevent these effects, the degree of their manifestation will influence the decision on whether this risk will be insured. If the possibility of adverse selection and/or opportunistic behavior is high enough, insurance companies will not want to take such a risk.

Insufficient definition of the criteria for choosing insurance as an economic risk management tool does not allow to classify risks into those that are subject to insurance and those that can be insured. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a more thor-

ough analysis of this issue. In the absence of unambiguous, objective criteria, the following rules should be used:

1. If it is possible to ensure a certain risk (standard insurance policies for the relevant risks and there is no alternative), insurance should be preferred, because creating or adapting another approach will be more expensive and less effective.

2. If the relevant risks are not subject to insurance and there is another option for combating their negative consequences, concluding insurance contracts may be ineffective. This will be associated with high transaction costs and premiums, which the insurance company will try to provide to protect against the possible risks of conducting uncertain operations.

Depending on the possibility of using different methods of risk management, including insurance, the choice will depend on the results of the analysis of costs and profits for each of the methods. Insurance should be chosen if it is cheaper and more effective. Almost any risk can be insured if there is an insurance company that agrees to take it over. Even risks traditionally classified as non-insurable can be insured unless prohibited by law, such as risks associated with military activities.

The general advantages of insurance as an economic risk management tool include:

- reduction of risk and losses for individuals, legal entities and state bodies, which contributes to the acceleration of the development of the entire country;
- coverage of damage due to insurance payments. It allows the firm to extend operations during the implementation of risk without long interruptions in work and problems with financial stability;
- the relative cheapness of insurance compared to other methods of risk management;
- overcoming the limited capabilities of insurance companies with special approaches to the redistribution of responsibility for covering relevant losses among other insurance market participants;
- provision of tax benefits for insurance transactions.

Among the disadvantages of insurance as an economic tool of risk management, the following should be highlighted:

- the existence of an insurance contract reduces the interest of the primary risk bearer (the insured) in carrying out other measures related to risk management;

- negotiations regarding the conclusion of the contract may take a lot of time and require additional costs associated with obtaining information;

- advance nature of insurance service provision (insurance premiums are paid at the beginning of the term of the contract) although it is not known whether there will be a loss or whether the service itself will be provided;

- limitations of the capacity of the insurance market, the capacity of individual insurance companies, long settlement periods, the influence of the business cycle can prevent the receipt of effective insurance protection, etc.

Insurance in the hospitality industry is one of the most commonly used methods of risk management. It refers to risk financing methods, that is, it involves the creation of a special reserve fund designed to cover a possible loss. When conducting an insurance transaction, both parties pursue their own goals. For the primary risk bearer, the transfer of responsibility means reducing the uncertainty of the financial state associated with the burden of the corresponding risk. For an insurance organization, combining a large number of independent risks in one portfolio allows to reduce the uncertainty associated with loss coverage. Funds collected within the framework of special insurance funds from a large number of policyholders will be sufficient to cover losses, because the probability of simultaneous realization of all risks assumed by the insurance organization is extremely small.

Insurance is a very popular risk management tool in the field of tourism and hotel and restaurant services: it allows you to deal with risks of various nature (related to service, accommodation, accommodation, business, etc.); its organization is possible in various, sometimes very specific forms (starting from special types of risk redistribution and ending with standard contracts with insurance companies via the Internet); there is a developed market of insurance services – a whole branch of finance and their services, characterized by the presence of specialized firms engaged in relevant operations, the presence of division of labor among such firms, the existence of developed regional and global markets [5, 6, 9]. However, insurance as a method of risk management can compete with other instruments. At the same time, the choice between the use of insurance and the use of alternative methods will depend on the type of

risk, the effectiveness of risk analysis methods and their cost, the presence of legislative, institutional and budgetary restrictions, as well as on the solution of information support problems.

For individuals, insurance as a method of risk management is more important – they have fewer risk management tools at their disposal. In particular, methods of risk transfer other than insurance are quite expensive for private individuals (for example, risk outsourcing), and in some cases even impossible (for example, redistribution of mortality risk among other individuals). At the same time, insurance will be cheaper than creating one's own reserves (keeping money in a «bank»).

When making a decision on concluding an insurance contract, it is necessary to take into account a number of important aspects, which can be summarized in the form of the following main stages.

1. Selection of risks to be insured. This stage is part of the decision-making procedure regarding the choice of risk management methods. The analysis of the characteristics of various risks (danger, risk propensity, vulnerability and relationship with other risks), as well as the features of their information support, the magnitude of these risks and the costs associated with them, allows you to specify for each risk the most suitable method of combating it.

2. Choosing the type of insurance coverage. At this stage, a decision is made about which insurance protection the risk bearer would like to provide for each of the previously selected risks. At the same time, such criteria as the amount of insurance payments intended to cover the corresponding loss and the related restrictions that reduce the coverage, the peculiarities of settlement of insurance cases (terms, necessary documentation and other conditions), key terms of the future insurance contract should be taken into account. price range of insurance services, as well as a number of other aspects. At this stage, if possible, a quantitative assessment of the risks that are expected to be transferred to insurance should be carried out.

3. Choosing an insurance company. Taking into account the understanding of what risks and under what conditions can be transferred to insurance, the offers of various insurance companies are analyzed. The purpose of such an analysis is to choose a company that offers the best insurance conditions – the optimal combination of «price – cover-

age» and (or) more complete compliance of the insurance company's offer with the client's need for insurance protection, which was identified at the previous stages. At the same time, the insurance organization must have a certain level of financial stability, which guarantees the insured to fulfill its obligations to indemnify the loss.

4. Conducting negotiations on the terms of the insurance contract and its conclusion. This is a very important stage that allows realizing the previously identified need for insurance protection in the form of a legally correct transfer of responsibility for covering the loss. These negotiations primarily concern such quantitative parameters as the amount of insurance coverage (insurance sum), the amount of the insurance premium (contract value) and the term of insurance. However, they may also apply to other terms of the contract.

Strategies for conducting such negotiations can be completely different: from the adoption of a standard contract to the negotiation of a contract containing special conditions. The choice of strategy will be determined by the specifics of the risk, the size of the coverage, the possibility of the policyholder submitting additional data indicating a reduction in risk, the ability of the parties to negotiate and the assessment of alternative costs (for example, loss of time to agree terms). As a rule, large firms that conclude large contracts have more opportunities than private individuals to obtain discounts and other concessions from the insurance organization.

5. Analysis of the effectiveness of insurance and decision-making on renegotiation of the contract. This stage provides «feedback» with the remaining stages. In its framework, information is accumulated about the peculiarities of the performance of insurance contracts in the past, and the amount of insurance protection is compared with the specified data on the number of losses that are associated with the risk transferred to insurance. This allows for more effective organization of risk management in general and insurance in particular in the following periods. The result of the analysis of the effectiveness of the use of insurance in the past will be a decision about the expediency of insuring the relevant risks in general, only by this insurance company, only on current conditions.

The following risk functions are distinguished in the management process:

- preventive, which manifests itself in the constructive search for safe management methods in relation to known risks;
- protective, the essence of which consists in the search at the conscious and instinctive levels of methods and means of protection against unwanted manifestations of risks;
- speculative, which provides the opportunity to win in the event of a random or planned favorable coincidence of the circumstances of the occurrence of risk;
- socio-economic, related to the natural selection of the most effective risk subjects and methods of their actions.

The following strategic methods of risk management can be identified (Table 1). Although none of these methods ensures the complete exclusion of risk, some part of the risk remains on the subject's own support.

In fact, risk management is reduced to the management of the risk object in order to minimize losses. Tactical risk management is the identification, analysis of risks and decision-making in order to maximize the positive and minimize the negative consequences of risk events. The risk management process usually includes the following procedures.

Risk management planning – the process of making decisions regarding the application and planning of risk management for a specific object. This process may include decisions on organization, staffing of risk management procedures, selection of the best methodology, sources of information for risk identification, time interval for analyzing the situation.

Risk identification determines which risks can affect the facility and documents the characteristics of these risks. Risk identification is an iterative process. Initially, risk identification can be performed

partially by a group of analysts. Further, identification can be done by the main group of managers. Independent experts may participate in the final stage of the process to form an objective assessment. Possible responses can be determined during the risk identification process.

Risk assessment. Qualitative assessment is the identification and definition of risks that require a quick response. Such an assessment determines the degree of importance of the risk and the method of response, the conditions for the occurrence of risks and the determination of their impact on the object using standard methods and means. Using this analysis helps to partially avoid the uncertainty inherent in risk. Quantitative assessment of risks determines the probability of occurrence of risks and the impact of the consequences of these risks on the object of insurance (or other object), which allows you to make the right decision and avoid uncertainty.

The risk response strategy is the development of the concept, plans and methods of reducing the risky impact on the object. Such planning involves the development of preventive and protective measures that reduce the probability of risk occurrence and the severity of negative consequences. At this stage, insurance reserves are formed and loss coverage services are created.

Monitoring and control ensure monitoring of the facility, compliance with risk identification and assessment procedures, formation of sufficient insurance reserves and terms of the insurance contract when settling insurance losses.

To ensure the sustainable development of tourist regions, the main mechanism of risk management is environmental insurance of business activities [1, 6, 9, 12]. Ukraine's integration into the world economic community dictates the need to transition to new principles of environmental protection activ-

Table 1. Basic methods of risk management in the hospitality industry

Method	Tool	Example
1. Risk avoidance	Optimizing the type of activity, its location and structure	. Moving the risk object beyond the limits of the enterprise's allocation
2. Risk reduction	Preventive and protective measures	Installation of alarms, application of redundant security systems
3. Risk transformation (including distribution)	Purposeful impact on the object and risk factors.	Distribution of the object in space to exclude the accumulation of losses, personal insurance
4. Transfer of risk	Conclusion of a special contract	Outsourcing, property insurance
5. Acceptance of risk	Forecast of risks and preparation for them of the object of risk	Strengthening resistance to risk (seismic resistance of buildings, etc.)

ity regulation and the development of a regulatory and legal system aimed at reducing the scale of industrial environmental pollution. The experience of developed countries shows that the most effective tool for environmental policy and guarantees of the safety of people's lives is the use of market mechanisms to protect the health of citizens and the environment. Funding expenses for liquidation of the consequences of accidents and emergency situations at the expense of budget funds reduces the effectiveness of environmental protection programs. This determines the need to find and mobilize fundamentally other sources of compensation for the damage caused.

Liability insurance for environmental pollution most effectively protects the interests of profit-making enterprises, society in protecting people's health, and the state through the creation of a favorable investment climate, guarantees of tax revenues and social stability. However, environmental risk insurance in Ukraine has not become widespread due to the lack of funds, as well as the insufficient level of regulatory and legal support for environmental protection measures and financial responsibility for violations of environmental norms and standards. Legal guarantees of compensation for damages caused by environmental pollution and reduction of the quality of natural resources are not fully provided. Ecological «green» taxes should be accumulated in special funds used to overcome these problems.

In addition to legal ones, the development of the environmental insurance market is hampered by:

- weak incentives for voluntary insurance;
- lack of reliable and generally accepted methods of risk assessment and calculation of probable damage;
- the low capacity of the market itself, which does not allow insurance of dangerous and large environmental losses [6, 9].

The most important thing to do now is to introduce the principle of unconditional liability for environmental damage caused by any business entities, as well as in wartime by military actions. This is the main global trend in the field of environmental liability legislation. Under such conditions, it is not necessary to prove that the violator acted illegally or negligently.

Recently, Ukraine began to pay more attention to the problems of financial support of environmental policy. Liability for environmental pollution or disturbance of landscapes is established by many

current legislative acts, which lay the foundations for mandatory insurance, for example, in the case of transportation of hazardous substances and operation of high-risk facilities. Insurance products developed on the basis of legislation on environmental protection are the first serious experience of applying the market mechanism for solving environmental problems in Ukraine. However, mandatory insurance gives the greatest result only when it is based on the generalization and analysis of the practice of voluntary insurance. In the absence of a strong voluntary environmental insurance market in Ukraine, the establishment of a mandatory form may not give the expected result. The main attention should be focused not on the obligation of insurance, but on the formation of incentives for the financial provision of obligations to compensate for damages from accidents and emergency situations. This will provide opportunities:

- reduce budget costs for liquidation of emergency and emergency situations;
- to increase the material responsibility of enterprises and the interest of local authorities in minimizing the negative impact on the environment;
- to ensure the targeted use of funds directed to the elimination of consequences and prevention of environmental pollution;
- strengthen control over potentially dangerous types of activities and make environmental safety requirements more stringent.

Environmental insurance includes a set of separate instruments that provide for the liability of the insurer for the risks associated with the violation of environmental legislation. They include:

1. Liability insurance in case of unforeseen force majeure environmental pollution.
2. Property insurance for financial losses caused by negative external effects of any economic activity, including military actions.
3. Personal life, health, disability and pension insurance of citizens in the event of a military-technogenic or natural disaster.
4. Liability insurance of tanker owners for the leakage of oil products and their pollution of waters and coasts.
5. Liability insurance of enterprises for damage caused to third parties in the process of using nuclear energy.
6. Liability insurance of enterprises for pollution of groundwater, agricultural land, and air.

7. Liability insurance for damage from mining activities of enterprises, etc. [9, 21].

The objects of environmental insurance are any environmental risks associated with the violation of environmental legislation and the infliction of potential economic damage caused by pollution with industrial, household and other waste, vehicles, as well as the violation of the integrity of the landscape and the deterioration of the quality of ecological systems at:

- placement, design, construction, reconstruction, commissioning and operation of enterprises, structures and other objects;
- use of plant protection products, mineral fertilizers, toxic chemicals, etc.;
- use and creation of new biologically active substances and means of biotechnology;
- effects of acoustic, electromagnetic, ionizing and other harmful physical factors;
- emissions of radioactive substances;
- transit transportation and placement on the territory of Ukraine of environmentally hazardous materials of both domestic and foreign production;
- conducting fundamental and applied scientific developments;
- introduction of equipment with increased ecological danger;
- conducting military operations in the territories of the community.

Environmental risk insurance is aimed at:

- formation of environmental responsibility of individuals and legal entities for the negative consequences of anthropogenic activity;
- stimulation of anti-accident measures due to the differentiation of insurance tariffs and cash payments for accident-free work;
- provision of compensation payments to victims regardless of the financial status of the perpetrator of harmful effects on the environment;
- ensuring stability of the financial condition of enterprises if necessary to compensate the victims of accidental pollution of the environment;
- provision of legal guarantees of financial protection of individuals and legal entities at the expense of established insurance funds.

That is, the purpose of environmental insurance is to protect the property interests of citizens and legal entities from damage that occurs in the event of deterioration of the environment and the quality of natural resources, and in the traditional sense,

it is a type of personal and property risk insurance. At the same time, in the system of environmental risk management, insurance is defined as the transfer of responsibility of enterprises—sources of increased environmental danger or «owners» of harmful objects, which pose a potential environmental threat to the lives of citizens and commercial interests of legal entities, to insurance companies. However, the nature protection purpose of environmental insurance remains a priority, and the main task is to compensate policyholders and third parties for damages caused by pollution of the natural environment.

The mechanism of environmental insurance is based on the principles of mutually beneficial relations between the insurer and the insured. In addition to the economic interest in transferring responsibility for negative consequences to the insurer, the insured is interested in increasing its environmental safety, since its own opportunities to solve the created problems may be limited due to the lack of: resources and qualified specialists.

Insurance rates differ depending on:

- degree of environmental risk;
- specifics of the economic activity of a certain policyholder;
- technical condition of production means (assets);
- availability and condition of protective and cleaning facilities at the enterprise;
- minimum and maximum amount of compensation.

If the damage occurred as a result of natural phenomena or deliberate actions of the victims, enterprises may be exempted from compensation for damage caused to the surrounding natural environment. In the event that the enterprise does not belong to the sources of increased danger, then they are exempted from damage coverage, provided they prove that the damage was caused through no fault of theirs. Victims have the right to compensation for lost profits for the time needed to restore the quality of the natural environment, restore natural resources to a state suitable for use as intended.

Simultaneously with the emergence of the environmental insurance market, the reinsurance market began to develop. In order to provide more extensive coverage and ensure substantial payments, special insurance pools have begun to be formed, which accumulate significant funds. The state also participates in the creation of pools. In Ukraine, in 1997, the National Nuclear Insurance

Pool for insurance of radioactive risks was created. Liability insurance for damage to the environment is carried out under the following conditions:

- full compensation to the insured of all amounts awarded by law to third parties in connection with the occurrence of an insured event, including court costs;
- insurance covers only losses as a result of accidental pollution;
- fines are not included in insurance coverage.

Insurers limit liability to a maximum amount of money and time period, because environmental insurance is quite complicated. A certain insurance policy can cover not only accidental pollution, but also the risk of permanent pollution. At the risk of gradual permanent pollution, the question arises about the degree of responsibility of other possible culprits. As a rule, insurance coverage refers to compensation for damage to third parties, so the insurer does not reimburse the costs of preventive measures or cleaning of the insured's own property.

In the field of ensuring radiological safety, there is a practice of nuclear risk insurance in Ukraine, which is carried out within the framework of the Vienna Convention on Civil Liability for Nuclear Damage, to which Ukraine joined in 1996. For this purpose, the National Nuclear Insurance Pool for Nuclear Risk Insurance was created in Ukraine. In accordance with the Convention, along with insurance, other (non-insurance) financial support for nuclear risks is used.

In order to ensure environmental safety and compensate victims for material and financial losses, it would be advisable to develop a special mechanism for the formation of industry insurance pools for the storage and effective use of reserve funds.

Conclusions

In the conditions of financial and economic crises, in particular, in force majeure circumstances of business, insurance acquires special importance as an economic tool of risk management. Important for business is the concept of «economic risk», which is defined as the possibility of accidental occurrence of unwanted losses, measured in value equivalent. To give this concept an operational meaning, it is necessary to classify risks according to various criteria, which can be built on the basis of the structural characteristics of the risk, the specifics of information support, and the features of risk measurement. For certain risks, it is also possible to use not

only general, but also specific classification criteria closely related to the specifics of the risks. In this context, the classification of risks according to adequately selected criteria can improve the identification of sources of economic risk and the choice of methods for its minimization. Environmental insurance provides financial and social protection of the population; stimulates business activity and the development of scientific and technical progress; supports macro-, microeconomic and financial stability, frees the state from many costs associated with various risks, and is an important institutional investor in the economy of an individual enterprise and the country as a whole. However, insurance as a risk management tool is not universal, its use has its limitations, which may be related to the type of risk, the mutual relations of the parties to the insurance transaction, and their attitude to risk. The risk management system can be implemented at the level of the state, firm and individual. These levels will differ in the nature and risk carriers, the specifics of the applied risk management measures.

The risk management system at the state level can be focused on different risks depending on the composition and content of state functions. Most often, they include ensuring sovereignty, external and environmental security, maintaining law and order and protecting the rights of citizens, facilitating the functioning and organizing the work of a number of important public institutions that serve the population as a whole. An important feature of the risk management system at the state level is the use of methods related to the risk reduction procedure, since the state's ability to avoid risk and transfer risk is quite limited. At the firm level, the risk management system is an integral part of general management. This is manifested both at the level of strategy and organizational structure of the firm. In some cases, outsourcing the risk management process is effective. The risk management tool in this case will be a risk management program. Its compilation and implementation in accordance with the content of the main stages and stages of development, procedures and methods of risk management, as well as the sequence of their application will allow the effective development of any company in the hospitality industry and will contribute to its financial stability. At the level of individuals, the risk management system is determined by the specifics of risks related to life and health, as well as property and liability of citi-

zens. At the state level, an important feature of the risk management system is the involvement of risk reduction methods, since the state's ability to avoid risk during war and to transfer risk to third parties is quite limited. At the macroeconomic level, it is expedient to create state sectoral insurance funds with the involvement of foreign reparation funds. Outsourcing the risk management process is particularly effective. The instrument of risk management in this case will be the state program of risk management and minimization after the war period.

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МАРТИНЕНКО В.П.
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Функції управління маркетинговою діяльністю підприємства

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні та практичні аспекти щодо визначення функцій управління маркетинговою діяльністю підприємства.

Метою дослідження є визначення та дослідження основних функцій управління маркетинговою діяльністю підприємства.

Методи дослідження. В процесі написання статті було використано наступні методи: абстрактно-логічний, систематизації та групування.

Результати роботи. В результаті проведеного дослідження було узагальнено підходи науковців щодо управління маркетинговою діяльністю на підприємствах як науковий напрям дослідження.

В науковій статті розкрито сутність управління маркетингом, визначено, що дане управління здійснюється на двох рівнях: стратегічному та тактичному. На стратегічному рівні визначається маркетингова стратегія підприємства. На тактичному рівні формується тактика маркетингу, орієнтована на формування ринкового попиту на товари та послуги підприємства.

Зазначено, що процес управління маркетингом на підприємстві має дві основні цілі. Перша пов'язана з реалізацією завдань, що стоять перед підприємством, а друга – з встановленням і підтримкою контактів зі споживачами.

В роботі визначені основні функції управління маркетинговою діяльністю суб'єкта господарювання, до яких належать: аналітична функція, розробка стратегічних та тактичних планів маркетингу, організація маркетингової діяльності та маркетингове мотивування, інформаційне забезпечення, маркетинговий контроль.

Представлено змістовні характеристики вищезазначених функцій, за допомогою яких формується система управління маркетингом і зазначено, що дані функції реалізуються, коли присутні цілісність і систематичність у підході до процесу управління на підприємстві.

Галузь застосування результатів. Маркетинг, управління, економіка підприємства.

Висновки. В результаті проведеного дослідження в науковій статті було визначено основні функції управління маркетинговою діяльністю, завдяки яким на підприємстві визначаються потреби споживачів продукції та зміни в ринковому середовищі, здійснюється стимулювання покупців, партнерів по